

Histories of Municipalities within Chenango County

DONALD A. WINDSOR

A municipality is an inhabited area that is incorporated, has its own elected government, and has definite boundaries.

The history of Chenango County is rich for some municipalities, but very meager for others. The basic early history by Smith 1880 covers every municipality from its origin to the mid 1870s. However, from then on the coverage is quite lopsided. Chenango County has 21 towns, 8 villages, and 1 city. We need a history for each of these 30 municipalities. I present here a table of at least one written history for each. To have a truly comprehensive county history we need to shore up our weak spots. First, let us review what we do have. See Table 1.

Hamlets are not incorporated, have no elected officials, and no boundaries. Hamlets are analogous to neighborhoods in a city. We do have some histories for them. See Table 2.

Most of the documents cited in these tables are books. Plenty of historical information is available in both published and unpublished records. I favored books because they are usually more carefully thought out and usually tell a story. History is the story of something over a time span. Chasing down individual records is like buying furniture that must be assembled. It takes a lot more work, eats up a lot of time, and is fraught with frustration. When I could find no books for a municipality, I used records.

Many of the books cited here are inadequate, because they have no indexes and some do not even tell a story. When an author neglects to provide an index it indicates that the book was intended to be merely a one-time read, not a reference source.

Table 1. Written histories of the municipalities in Chenango County.

Municipality	Written history
Chenango County	Clark 1850 Smith 1880 Lynch 1929
Afton	Hayes 1976
Bainbridge	Colwell 1946 Danforth 1987
Columbus	Avery 1994
Coventry	Judd 1912
German	Huntly <i>Unpublished 1968</i> Anon <i>Unpublished 2002</i>
Greene	Cochrane 1967 Folsom 1971
Guilford	Gray multiple books 2001 -07-13 -16
Lincklaen	Poole 1994 -95 -96
McDonough	Tuttle <i>Unpublished 1939</i>
New Berlin	Hyde 1876 Wilber 1964 -67 -69 Avery 1994
North Norwich	Peck 1907 Sesquicentennial Book Committee 1999
Norwich	NONE
Otselic	Cox 2004 Davis 2016 -17
Oxford	Galpin 1906 Stafford 2002
Pharsalia	Jackson <i>Unpublished 1967 -73 -77</i>
Pitcher	Hagen 1954
Plymouth	Doing 1954
Preston	Kalicicki 1961
Sherburne	Hatch 1862 Wellman 2004
Smithville	NONE
Symrna	Munson 1905 Sprague <i>Unpublished 1963</i>
City of Norwich	Anon 1880 Shinners 1964 Phillips 1984 2002 Winter 2005 Storms 2014
Village of Afton	NONE

Table 1. Continued

Municipality	Written history
Village of Bainbridge	Danforth 1987
Village of Earlville	
Village of Greene	
Village of New Berlin	
Village of Oxford	Lanfear 2011
Village of Sherburne	Gomph 1896
	Benedict 1996
Village of Smyrna	

Scrapbooks are bountiful, but they tell no story. They just show one thing after another. However, sometimes a scrapbook is all we have and so, it is better than nothing.

Three books are unpublished manuscripts. I suspect that the authors died before they could finish. They should be published.

Three towns (Norwich, Plymouth, and Smithville) have no histories beyond what appears in Smith 1880. Three towns (German, Otselic, and Pharsalia) have woefully inadequate histories. I find this appalling and will try to solicit authors.

Five of our eight villages have no histories of their own but are covered in their town histories.

We have about a hundred hamlets, but only seven have histories.

The lopsidedness of Chenango County history is shown in Table 3. Of its 22 town-level municipalities (21 towns plus 1 city) only 8 (36.4%) are

Table 2.

Hamlet	Town	Written history
Chenango Lake	New Berlin	Gibson 2007 -09
Guilford	Guilford	Gray 2013
Guilford Center	Guilford	Gray 2001
Mount Upton	Guilford	Gray 2016
North Guilford	Guilford	Palen 1946
Pitcher Springs	Pitcher	Hagen 1954
Rockwells Mills	Guilford	Gray 2007
Woods Corners	Norwich	Tiffany 2010

Table 3. My appraisals for the 21 towns. The City of Norwich is included because it is equivalent to a town. Criteria are for published documents only, nothing else.

Towns	Appraisal	Appraisal	Percent	Cumulative %
Guilford	*****	↓		
City of Norwich	*****	2 are Superb	9.1%	9.1%
Greene	****	↓		
New Berlin	****	2 are Good	9.1%	18.2%
Bainbridge	***	↓		
North Norwich	***	↓		
Oxford	***	↓		
Sherburne	***	4 are Adequate	18.2%	36.4%
Columbus	**	↓		
McDonough	**	↓		
Otselic	**	↓		
Preston	**	↓		
Symrna	**	5 are Basic	22.7%	59.1%
Afton	*	↓		
Coventry	*	↓		
Lincklaen	*	↓		
Plymouth	*	↓		
Pharsalia	*	↓		
Pitcher	*	6 are Inadequate	27.3%	86.4%
German	0	↓		
Norwich	0	↓		
Smithville	0	3 are Woeful	13.6%	100.0%
Totals		22	100.0%	100.0%

***** = Superb. A detailed history is well explained and recent.

**** = Good. The history is explained.

*** = Adequate. Enriched basics and recent.

** = Basic. Just enough to get by.

* = Inadequate. At least there is some history, not much, but some.

0 = Woefully inadequate.

adequate or better. A whopping 14 (63.6%) are worse than adequate. Sad to say, but 3 (13.6%) are woefully inadequate.

Anyone who knows of additional histories is encouraged to notify the author. Anyone who wants to write a history is enthusiastically encouraged to contact the editor. Both the author of this article and the editor of this journal are united in their quest to get more histories published.

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